

SUMO1/sentrin/SMT3 specific peptidase 2 (SEN2/AXAM2) : Time behavioural study of 3rd order combinations in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells

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Abstract

SEN2 is cysteine protease that belongs to the family of sentrin-specific protease, which come under the broader group of SUMO-specific isopeptidases and proteases. The ubiquitin-like SUMO (small ubiquitin-related modifier) system is a post-translational protein modification pathway in eukaryotes, where SUMOylation is a highly dynamic process and deconjugation (deSUMOylation) is catalyzed by a family of cysteine proteases, termed SUMO-specific proteases or SUMO isopeptidases. SEN2 processes newly synthesized SUMO1 into the conjugatable form and catalyze the deconjugation of SUMO1-containing species. Gujral and MacBeath [1] provides a quantitative, and dynamic study of WNT3A-mediated stimulation of HEK 293 cells, where they record time based expression profiles of several response genes which correlated significantly with proliferation and migration. By monitoring the dynamics of gene expression using self-organizing maps, they identified clusters of genes that exhibit similar expression dynamics and uncovered previously unrecognized positive and negative feedback loops. However, their study depicts/uses singular measurements of individual gene expression at different time snapshots/points to infer the system wide analysis of the pathway. At any particular time point, it is often the case that genes are working synergistically in combinations, even though their expression measurements are singular in nature. Here, I • enumerate and rank all 2415 SEN2 related 3rd order combinations in a forest of ${}^{71}C_3$ combinations using four different sensitivity methods; • show the conserved rankings for SEN2-X-X combinations, which point to existence of biological synergy of some of these combinations across the different sensitivity methods; and • study the behaviour of some of these combinations related to WNT3A response genes that are ranked by the machine learning search engine (Sinha [2]) in time. Patterns of combinations emerge, some of which have been tested in wet lab, while others require further wet lab analysis.

[☆]Time behavioural study of 3-odr SEN2 comb. in WNT3A stimulated cells

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1. Significance

Sinha [2] recently demonstrated the use of machine learning based search engine to rank/reveal gene combinations at 2nd order for the time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1] and showed how it is possible to locate combinations of priority that might be working synergistically, using sensitivity methods and powerful support vector ranking algorithm. However, the problem explodes combinatorially with even a small set of 71 recorded genes in the study by Gujral and MacBeath [1], when one steps to explore 3rd order combinations. With the total number of ${}^{71}C_3$ (= 57155) combinations, it becomes nearly impossible for any biologist to study the system wide dynamics of any pathway. Also, the amount of time usually needed to search for and test a combination is far more than the search down by the machine learning based search engine. Here, I extend the research work by Sinha [2] to conduct a behavioral study of 3rd order SENP2 related combinations using individual gene expressions measured in time, in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells.

2. Introduction

The details of the machine learning based search engine has been recently published in Sinha [2] and deployed to explore the 2nd order combinations of genes in the data set provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. Nevertheless, here, I point to the fundamentals of the published work for completeness.

2.1. A combinatorial problem

Sensitivity analysis plays a major role in computing the strength of the influence of involved factors in any phenomena under investigation. When applied to expression profiles of various intra/extracellular factors that form an integral part of a signaling pathway, the variance and density based analysis yields a range of sensitivity indices for individual as well as various combinations of factors. These combinations denote the higher order interactions among the involved factors. Computation of higher order interactions is often time consuming but it gives a chance to explore the various combinations that might be of interest in the working mechanism of the pathway. For example, in a range of fourth order combinations among the various factors of the Wnt pathway, it would be easy to assess the influence of the destruction complex formed by APC, AXIN, CSKI and GSK3 interaction. But the effect of these combinations vary over time as measurements of fold changes and deviations in fold changes vary. So it is imperative to know how an interaction or a combination of the involved factors behave in time and Sinha [2] develops a procedure to track the behaviour by exploiting the influences of these involved factors.

2.2. A possible solution

In this work, after estimating the individual effects of factors for a higher order combination, the individual indices are considered as discriminative features. A combination, then, is a feature set in higher order (≥ 2 , i.e. multivariate). With an excessively large number of factors involved in the pathway, it is difficult to search for important combinations in a wide search space over different orders. Exploiting the analogy with the issues of prioritizing webpages using ranking algorithms, for a particular order, a full set of combinations of interactions can then be prioritized based on these features using a powerful ranking algorithm via support vectors Joachims [3]. Recording the changing rankings of the combinations over time reveals how higher order interactions behave within the pathway and when an intervention might be necessary to influence the interaction within the pathway.

2.3. SUMO1/sentrin/SMT3 specific peptidase 2 (SEN2)

Posttranslational modification with small ubiquitin-related modifier (SUMO) proteins is a key regulatory protein modifications in eukaryotic cells where, proteins involved in processes like chromatin organization, transcription, DNA repair, macromolecular assembly, protein homeostasis, trafficking, and signal transduction are subject to reversible sumoylation. Flotho and Melchior [4] summarize basic mechanisms and highlight recent developments in the physiology of sumoylation. Gareau and Lima [5] elucidate an understanding of SUMO regulatory mechanisms which might lead to improved approaches for analysing the function of SUMO and substrate conjugation in distinct cellular pathways. In a summary on SENPs, Nayak and Muller [6] state that the known SUMO-specific isopeptidases and proteases are cysteine proteases that are classified into three distinct families: • the Ulp/SEN2 (ubiquitin-like protease/sentrin-specific protease) family, • the Des1 (deSUMOylating isopeptidase) family and • USPL1 (ubiquitin-specific peptidase-like protein 1).

Briefly, Gareau and Lima [5] elucidate the SUMO conjugation cycle in a few steps, which i reiterate for completeness (For graphical understanding please see figure 1 in Gareau and Lima [5]). • SUMO undergoes processing by Ulp and SEN2s to its mature form, thus revealing a carboxy-terminal Gly-Gly motif. • SUMO is then adenylated by the SUMO-activating enzyme subunit 1 (SAE1)-ubiquitin-like activating enzyme subunit 2 (UBA2) E1 complex in an $\text{ATP} \circ \text{Mg}^{2+}$ -dependent reaction and transferred to the catalytic Cys of the UBA2 subunit; • Following activation, SUMO is transferred to the catalytic Cys of the E2 conjugating enzyme, ubiquitin-like conjugating enzyme 9 (UBC9). • It can then catalyze conjugation to a substrate in an E3 ligase-independent manner through recognition of SUMO consensus motifs (ΨKXE) that contain a Lys acceptor residue. In addition, SUMO ligases can facilitate SUMO transfer through distinct mechanisms. The authors depict three different mechanism for this from steps 5 to 7 in figure 1 of Gareau and Lima [5]. Substrate specificity imparted by E3-substrate interactions are thought to be particularly important for directing conjugation to non-consensus Lys residues. • Substrates modified by SUMO can contact SUMO-binding proteins through their SUMO-interacting motifs (SIMs). Finally, • Deconjugation is performed by Ulp and SEN2 proteases and free SUMO may be recycled for another

round of conjugation.

AXIN forms a complex with adenomatous polyposis coli (APC) gene product, glycogen synthase kinase-3b (GSK3 β), β -catenin, DVL, and protein phosphatase 2A (PP2A) and functions as a scaffold protein in the WNT signaling pathway. In the AXIN complex, GSK3 β phosphorylates β -catenin, which is then ubiquitinated and degraded by proteasome. Kadoya et al. [7] isolated a novel protein that binds to AXIN and named it AXAM (for Axin associating molecule). AXAM formed a complex with AXIN in intact cells and bound directly to AXIN, thus inhibiting the complex formation of DVL with AXIN and the activity of DVL to suppress GSK3 β -dependent phosphorylation of AXIN. Furthermore, they observed that AXAM induced the degradation of β -catenin in SW480 cells and inhibited WNT-dependent axis duplication in *Xenopus* embryos. Their results suggested that AXAM regulates the WNT signaling pathway negatively by inhibiting the binding of DVL to AXIN.

Nishida et al. [8] cloned and characterized SUMO-1/Smt3-specific isopeptidase, SMT3IP2/AXAM2 (Smt3-specific isopeptidase 2). The sequence data indicated that the amino acid sequence of SMT3IP2 was mostly identical to that of rat AXAM, which binds to AXIN and promotes the degradation of β -catenin. Based on this, the authors designated this isopeptidase SMT3IP2/AXAM2. Further, when human SW480 cells were transfected with wild-type SMT3IP2/AXAM2, β -catenin disappeared. Also, it was observed that when the cells were transfected with the SMT3IP2/AXAM2 C500A mutant, which had neither isopeptidase nor carboxyl-terminal hydrolase activity, or with the 1-352 mutant, which lacked the catalytic domain of the enzyme, again β -catenin disappeared, indicating that the enzyme activities were not necessary for the instability of β -catenin in this transfection assay system and that its competition with DVL for binding to AXIN may be important for the instability of β -catenin as suggested previously for AXAM by Kadoya et al. [7].

AXAM induces the degradation of β -catenin in SW480 cells (human colon cancer cells) and inhibits axis formation in *Xenopus* embryos. Kadoya et al. [9] show that AXAM has the catalytic activity to remove SUMO-1 from sumoylated proteins and that its mutant without this activity is less able to downregulate β -catenin and to inhibit axis formation of *Xenopus* embryos. Their results demonstrate that AXAM functions as a desumoylation enzyme to downregulate β -catenin in mammalian cells and suggest that sumoylation is involved in the regulation of the WNT signaling pathway.

I present 3rd order combinations of SENP2 with other genes, that the machine learning based search engine points to, as possible synergistic combinations that might be working in time.

3. Methods

Please refer to sections of Sinha [2] for methods, design of study and analysis of data for 2nd order combinations. The same method and design of study is used to generate results for 3rd order combinations presented in this study.

4. Time series data

Gujral and MacBeath [1] present a set of 71 WNT-related gene expression values for 6 different time points over a range of 24-hour period using qPCR. The changes represent the fold-change in the expression levels of genes in 200 ng/mL WNT3A-stimulated HEK 293 cells in time relative to their levels in unstimulated, serum-starved cells at 0-hour. Gujral and MacBeath [1] state that qPCR data are the means of three biological replicates. Only genes whose mean transcript levels changed by more than two-fold at one or more time points during the 24-hour time course were considered significant. Positive (negative) numbers represent up (down) -regulation. We have already covered the issues related to these data sets in detail in Sinha [10]. Readers are requested to go through them in the pointed reference. The tools of study which are used here have been published in another foundational work in Sinha [10].

5. Design of experiment

5.1. Pipeline for time series data

For the case of time series data, interactions among the contributing factors are studied by comparing triplets of fold-changes at single time points. The procedure begins with the generation of distribution around measurements at single time points with added noise is done to estimate the indices. A distribution is generated for the fold changes at single time points. Then for every gene, there is a vector of values representing fold changes as well as deviations in fold changes for different time points and durations between time points, respectively. Next a listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes is generated. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represents a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. After this, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in the required format from the distributions for two separate cases which have been discussed above. (See .R code in mainScript-1-1.R). After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations. This procedure is done for different kinds of sensitivity analysis methods.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Since there is only one recording of sensitivity index per combination, each combination forms a training example which is allotted a training index and the sensitivity indices of the individual genetic factors form the training example. Thus there are C_k^n training examples for k^{th} order interaction. Using this training set SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [3] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The

model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [3]. Note that due to availability of only one example per combination, after the model has been built, the same training data is used as test data to generate the scores. This procedure is executed for each and every sensitivity analysis method. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices (i.e the training indices) already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm. Finally, this entire procedure is computed for sensitivity indices generated for each and every fold change at time point and deviations in fold change at different durations. Observing the changing rank of a particular combination at different times and different time periods will reveal how a combination is behaving.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("mainScript-1-1.R") with arguments for Dynamic data • source("SVMRank-Results-D.R"), to rank the interactions (again this needs to be done separately for different kinds of SA methods), • use source("Combine-Time-files.R"), if computing indices separately via previous file, • source("Sort-n-Plot-D.R") to sort the interactions. Note that the sorting is changes the interaction ranking in time. Thus • use source("Interaction-Priority-Intime.R") to find the prioritized ranking of each and every interaction over the different time points and finally • use source("Print-Ranking-AND-Interaction-Rank.R") to print individual ranking of the required input factor with other interaction factors.

6. Results & Discussion

6.1. Time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1]

NOTE - Ranking was assigned on scores that were sorted in DECREASING values. So, 1 was assigned to highest score and vice versa.

Results for the 3rd order interactions are presented here. The results first discuss the behaviour of interactions across the snapshots of time using the computed sensitivities on fold change measurements per time snapshot. The analysis was done using 4 different sensitivity indices. Out of the 7C_3 combinations, I consider/present only those combinations that show a ranking within first 10,000 out of 57,155. This choice is liberal and biologists/oncologists can have a more stricter choice as per need. Two observations are made, • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved (i.e within the 10,000 range) in a particular time point or in the early phase or late phase of WNT3A stimulation, across the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is a strict criteria of assessment or • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved across time points/phase (i.e they are within the 10,000 range) and the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is relaxed criteria of assessment. Applying this filter helps reveal important combinations of interest that might be working synergistically at a higher order level in the cell.

Regarding technical points of implementation, the rankings were generated without scaling/normalizing the time series data provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1].

For estimating the sensitivity indices, a small gaussian distribution using the function **rnorm** that generates a vector of normally distributed random variables given a vector length n (here 9, the 10th one is the mean/recorded gene regulation itself), a population mean μ and population standard deviation σ . The syntax for using **rnorm** is as follows: **rnorm(n, mean, sd)**. Further, I use the **jitter** function to add a little bit of noise to the data. This helps to see if the generated rankings are robust or not.

6.2. Enumeration and ranking of 2415 SENP2-X-X combinations from Gujral and MacBeath [1]

In the supplementary section, I present four files, each containing the rankings of 3rd order combinations, that vary in time (shown for 5 time points). Each file represents the rankings computed using a particular sensitivity method. The changing rankings in time for a particular combination represents the importance of contribution/role that combination plays in the cell stimulated with WNT3A. The sensitivity methods used are Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) indices (with rbf and linear kernel in Da Veiga [11]) and Sobol indices (with 2002 implementation in Saltelli [12] and martinez implementation in Martinez [13] and Baudin et al. [14]).

6.3. Conserved machine learning rankings for tested SENP2-X-X combinations

A total of 2415, 3rd order combinations involving SENP2 were obtained from a full set of ${}^{71}C_3 = 57155$ combinations. Further, from this selected set, using the above criteria for conserved rankings, I report/tabulate the meaningful combinations that might be working synergistically. Tables 2, 3 and 4 show the rankings for the same combinations as in table 1, but using rbf kernel for HSIC, 2002 implementation for SOBOL and martinez implementation for SOBOL, respectively. As one tallies the rankings of across these tables for a particular combination, one finds that the role of the combination of interest is conserved. This conservation points to the existence of the biological synergy, whether the combination has been tested or unexplored/untested.

6.3.1. Examining the behaviour of AXIN1-SENP2-X combinations

In the above literature review, it shown that SENP2 binds with AXIN. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for AXIN1 along with SENP2, to be prominent at 3rd order level - AXIN1-FZD2-SENP2 and AXIN1-MYC-SENP2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.2. Examining the behaviour of DVL-SENP2-X combinations

Further, due to the above binding of SENP2 with AXIN, SENP2 inhibits the formation of complex of AXIN with DVL, which reduces the functioning of the WNT pathway. This negative synergy between SENP2 and DVL also gives insight as to which combination of DVL-SENP2 is getting affected at a particular time. Looking at the tables

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - LINEAR

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FBXW11-LRP6-SEN2	1	34823	45217	17593	40419	DKK1-JUN-SEN2	3	13146	45291	34681	42815
CXXC4-PORCN-SEN2	10	33446	17033	17387	32253	CSNK1D-FGF4-SEN2	12	15434	36642	38886	8419
CSNK2A1-MYC-SEN2	13	32182	51840	11657	9637	FOSL1-FRAT1-SEN2	24	25444	38488	23401	24549
APC-FZD6-SEN2	26	11930	12152	51400	36485	APC-PITX2-SEN2	37	14630	40719	18877	15582
DVL2-JUN-SEN2	40	7571	46728	17699	4151	FZD1-NLK-SEN2	66	7254	6519	12561	16204
DKK1-DVL2-SEN2	73	6472	32886	33074	53536	CSNK1G1-NLK-SEN2	74	35675	3308	48520	19328
FZD7-NKD1-SEN2	78	10179	4761	28020	28474	CCND2-LRP6-SEN2	83	56244	18182	20944	394
CXXC4-FOSL1-SEN2	88	36639	18548	29008	12844	LRP5-NLK-SEN2	99	17426	20510	156	54321
FRZB-JUN-SEN2	109	12704	33983	8160	2937	DKK1-LRP6-SEN2	117	30001	55075	39664	8461
DIXDC1-NKD1-SEN2	139	26878	5252	13422	20937	CTBP2-CTNNB1-SEN2	141	36145	41533	3064	6745
DAAMI-LRP6-SEN2	142	53280	45015	4819	36940	FZD5-CCND2-SEN2	150	29656	19798	20159	54229
FSHB-FZD2-SEN2	155	15792	56338	24860	16086	FZD5-CCND3-SEN2	179	12580	12647	25661	981
FZD7-PORCN-SEN2	204	27924	5434	9587	14745	DKK1-PYGO1-SEN2	253	27760	37224	42160	22797
CSNK1D-PORCN-SEN2	254	26488	43944	21480	22511	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SEN2	256	39545	1842	16944	18375
FRZB-MYC-SEN2	259	14872	1551	37339	16113	AES-EP300-SEN2	266	39979	55044	31248	12673
SEN2-FBXW4-WNT3A	274	39131	29	44525	46327	DKK1-MYC-SEN2	288	24145	39527	40800	42346
FBXW2-PYGO1-SEN2	295	47321	21813	9500	57018	FRAT1-NLK-SEN2	308	14795	5137	12639	16597
FRZB-GSK3A-SEN2	323	15116	1689	3761	6417	CXXC4-FGF4-SEN2	325	44612	33138	54156	47148
DKK1-FOSL1-SEN2	326	21740	41468	36036	47108	FZD5-PITX2-SEN2	328	35236	22541	1156	14803
DKK1-FOXN1-SEN2	342	12351	29242	3585	34803	FOSL1-PORCN-SEN2	349	31659	11861	10245	21849
FZD5-MYC-SEN2	356	21029	5031	27635	17098	FOSL1-NLK-SEN2	359	18070	3202	3757	21594
DAAMI-PYGO1-SEN2	365	46893	25207	11837	39100	FZD5-PORCN-SEN2	377	32693	14759	8273	55426
FZD1-PORCN-SEN2	382	25494	17903	13765	16485	FBXW11-FOXN1-SEN2	392	5743	6882	5378	5741
DKK1-PORCN-SEN2	400	29700	53693	2734	52517	FRZB-FZD2-SEN2	403	12012	17053	8131	21847
CSNK1G1-PORCN-SEN2	410	36322	35831	12245	17913	CSNK1G1-FZD2-SEN2	430	26396	20526	35632	16355
DKK1-PPP2R1A-SEN2	442	14095	52078	45675	54675	CTNNB1P1-JUN-SEN2	451	45193	55478	33408	6827
FOSL1-JUN-SEN2	458	25557	50663	10786	1378	APC-PORCN-SEN2	466	12387	7261	13497	19215
FRZB-PORCN-SEN2	467	13159	11733	10122	22264	GSK3B-LRP6-SEN2	469	39713	22216	39819	33008
DVL1-MYC-SEN2	471	36864	4815	28745	33686	FZD5-FOXN1-SEN2	473	7569	6670	5785	7868
LRP5-PORCN-SEN2	476	41616	8750	51278	21981	FZD6-PORCN-SEN2	497	45212	45263	687	14394
AES-FOXN1-SEN2	518	22315	8527	7631	2724	DIXDC1-PITX2-SEN2	526	28707	7274	5676	35235
FZD7-PPP2CA-SEN2	540	11483	354	3539	34512	BCL9-FGF4-SEN2	548	29256	46172	46692	39145
FRZB-LRP5-SEN2	559	19130	1798	1543	5708	CTBP2-FOXN1-SEN2	566	19815	6401	2342	17983
FZD5-GSK3A-SEN2	569	25593	683	21843	18713	FSHB-NKD1-SEN2	574	7025	14205	7566	35992
DKK1-NKD1-SEN2	575	5975	43246	35996	27099	FZD5-PYGO1-SEN2	593	19014	1524	25504	36744
SEN2-TLE1-TLE2	610	6333	16429	15833	19287	FBXW11-NKD1-SEN2	618	34583	6281	9193	28276
CSNK1D-FOXN1-SEN2	624	4830	5783	7469	36423	FZD8-PORCN-SEN2	639	19701	11231	9109	12830
FBXW11-GSK3B-SEN2	640	23534	27154	19849	22130	DKK1-FSHB-SEN2	641	24808	11118	11901	46995
DKK1-FRAT1-SEN2	669	29229	40235	2545	51616	SEN2-WNT1-WNT2B	701	40779	2190	9179	41846
FRZB-NKD1-SEN2	705	6025	7511	12942	30682	CSNK1G1-DVL2-SEN2	708	9805	19546	23999	8201
FBXW11-FGF4-SEN2	711	39559	55606	33012	11315	FRZB-LEF1-SEN2	746	18406	20494	19809	3129
NLK-PORCN-SEN2	751	51440	56864	21216	6122	FZD5-FZD2-SEN2	769	23664	3575	3654	30814
FZD1-FZD2-SEN2	791	9528	30021	12952	33087	SEN2-SFRP1-WNT2B	804	39477	39510	38291	12235
FOSL1-FOXN1-SEN2	808	25273	3965	4409	8541	FBXW11-RHO-SEN2	810	39829	54582	1076	13192
CSNK1G1-LRP5-SEN2	821	46576	17464	17352	30361	CXXC4-JUN-SEN2	843	21048	50347	6595	9660
CSNK1G1-JUN-SEN2	855	23957	55112	11084	3256	FZD1-NKD1-SEN2	865	3117	15529	25963	26289
FRAT1-JUN-SEN2	876	27146	34459	14780	13983	SEN2-WNT1-WNT4	879	37625	2401	4412	29111
DVL1-FOXN1-SEN2	907	37314	6190	2465	34563	FRAT1-PORCN-SEN2	915	19198	9986	14436	18176
DVL1-FBXW11-SEN2	927	27739	8099	22915	52768	APC-FZD2-SEN2	934	24435	31374	10970	32370
FZD5-CTNNB1P1-SEN2	936	41581	21812	4533	34272	SEN2-FBXW4-WNT4	962	28442	9419	12651	42095
AXIN1-FZD2-SEN2	970	21704	36841	4481	4717	FRZB-FSHB-SEN2	1016	13136	7480	5202	23820
FRZB-LRP6-SEN2	1020	16728	2573	7208	6418	DKK1-LEF1-SEN2	1053	32782	23184	36091	24285
CSNK1G1-FSHB-SEN2	1054	47479	13640	1228	8996	KREMEN1-PORCN-SEN2	1055	20253	16697	487	37387
FZD7-GSK3A-SEN2	1057	22214	256	52631	33449	FSHB-GSK3A-SEN2	1073	16288	25162	18111	11005
FBXW11-JUN-SEN2	1078	21114	46139	41233	39344	EP300-GSK3B-SEN2	1093	42030	6696	7981	765
DIXDC1-LRP5-SEN2	1098	18807	1510	3942	4609	DAAMI-GSK3A-SEN2	1101	52332	26964	25607	49696
FZD1-GSK3A-SEN2	1104	10414	2123	23509	7420	DIXDC1-FZD2-SEN2	1148	28328	6949	7791	20834
AXIN1-MYC-SEN2	1162	8878	8434	19760	6540	CTBP1-GSK3A-SEN2	1213	25332	467	15589	11039
FBXW2-PORCN-SEN2	1224	33013	2285	41273	42593	FSHB-LEF1-SEN2	1229	12578	50301	24457	7777
GSK3B-RHO-SEN2	1230	39467	21376	11806	9365	CSNK2A1-FOXN1-SEN2	1233	22059	16672	4525	3145
FBXW2-JUN-SEN2	1253	32758	51631	42897	55749	CSNK1G1-NKD1-SEN2	1257	16631	15972	26700	19860
BTRC-GSK3A-SEN2	1269	31571	50158	24473	28342	FRZB-PYGO1-SEN2	1288	22336	2406	8695	20479
FBXW11-FBXW2-SEN2	1293	31516	16133	5700	35658	FZD8-GSK3A-SEN2	1313	24932	915	45683	16569

Table 1: Rankings of SEN2-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - linear

above, one finds the following combinations for members of the DVL family along with SEN2, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DVL2-JUN-SEN2, DKK1-DVL2-SEN2, DVL1-MYC-SEN2, DVL1-FOXN1-SEN2, DVL1-FBXW11-SEN2 and

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - RBF

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FBXW11-LRP6-SEN2	462	28989	38794	18690	24696	DKK1-JUN-SEN2	2445	33296	14766	10519	28087
CXXC4-PORCN-SEN2	9869	47028	41747	45009	41195	CSNK1D-FGF4-SEN2	2542	27165	19967	35638	32914
CSNK2A1-MYC-SEN2	698	26688	37719	17840	33212	FOSL1-FRAT1-SEN2	15910	20828	47008	39310	20122
APC-FZD6-SEN2	4000	27344	40691	10612	57100	APC-PITX2-SEN2	2251	31790	24604	4114	39754
DVL2-JUN-SEN2	4462	28972	39208	37581	33219	FZD1-NLK-SEN2	4216	33313	50995	20046	16713
DKK1-DVL2-SEN2	12170	26608	1445	16210	24013	CSNK1G1-NLK-SEN2	34480	34469	25805	4202	8014
FZD7-NKD1-SEN2	22248	3166	47262	13293	2567	CCND2-LRP6-SEN2	4694	56422	53343	22864	16505
CXXC4-FOSL1-SEN2	27232	42351	44650	16863	48178	LRP5-NLK-SEN2	28404	31921	48677	23545	26406
FRZB-JUN-SEN2	1481	18469	38799	27435	28090	DKK1-LRP6-SEN2	1861	37831	42104	4554	34077
DIXDC1-NKD1-SEN2	24325	22750	54264	38554	4248	CTBP2-CTNNB1-SEN2	20615	24125	47470	7727	18482
DAAMI-LRP6-SEN2	6978	55181	28837	993	26132	FZD5-CCND2-SEN2	1593	48667	56355	20858	31218
FSHB-FZD2-SEN2	722	17184	1804	8318	40473	FZD5-CCND3-SEN2	682	12899	44614	4156	28575
FZD7-PORCN-SEN2	12209	34605	55753	8086	12262	DKK1-PYGO1-SEN2	403	23098	9845	24707	36625
CSNK1D-PORCN-SEN2	5664	26748	24402	26200	37885	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SEN2	36531	47500	56688	1297	8711
FRZB-MYC-SEN2	341	12601	46519	38771	50004	AES-EP300-SEN2	36742	43851	9360	56088	25857
SEN2-FBXW4-WNT3A	27065	27541	40533	55578	8502	DKK1-MYC-SEN2	954	23283	49758	23572	34187
FBXW2-PYGO1-SEN2	5592	54522	7624	18559	15058	FRAT1-NLK-SEN2	47712	35472	55874	27952	35046
FRZB-GSK3A-SEN2	1005	18367	54917	45435	43654	CXXC4-FGF4-SEN2	252	42683	39239	31323	30294
DKK1-FOSL1-SEN2	14095	26375	3333	23119	42212	FZD5-PITX2-SEN2	10435	42695	24116	3954	33353
DKK1-FOXN1-SEN2	1097	45908	33686	6660	22662	FOSL1-PORCN-SEN2	314	29835	38646	3075	34319
FZD5-MYC-SEN2	4758	9532	47106	17393	47394	FOSL1-NLK-SEN2	41514	24088	54636	21014	19349
DAAMI-PYGO1-SEN2	7009	46420	6762	21944	29682	FZD5-PORCN-SEN2	13359	46673	16639	12543	32648
FZD1-PORCN-SEN2	5513	34056	9744	10153	31014	FBXW11-FOXN1-SEN2	128	6559	40566	11817	4361
DKK1-PORCN-SEN2	2598	41263	6134	19723	13188	FRZB-FZD2-SEN2	2112	16652	26767	43657	55251
CSNK1G1-PORCN-SEN2	13585	41454	10606	1967	17443	CSNK1G1-FZD2-SEN2	16568	22383	10213	6975	36119
DKK1-PPP2R1A-SEN2	4320	17195	24869	14464	3866	CTNNB1P1-JUN-SEN2	42259	50095	40291	21021	34386
FOSL1-JUN-SEN2	15271	29847	41615	22047	48378	APC-PORCN-SEN2	311	33317	27533	12463	51663
FRZB-PORCN-SEN2	2427	25944	18926	35699	48606	GSK3B-LRP6-SEN2	2447	36212	52160	19143	45638
DVL1-MYC-SEN2	2855	32356	46420	20795	31751	FZD5-FOXN1-SEN2	755	12834	53767	11567	34539
LRP5-PORCN-SEN2	11545	45801	9754	1937	37320	FZD6-PORCN-SEN2	3	53444	8379	12707	32509
AES-FOXN1-SEN2	1218	24082	52757	25404	14040	DIXDC1-PITX2-SEN2	3537	43865	15972	13329	19660
FZD7-PPP2CA-SEN2	32571	2154	49346	21000	26293	BCL9-FGF4-SEN2	7646	28217	10273	19350	40259
FRZB-LRP5-SEN2	555	19606	45855	1859	48730	CTBP2-FOXN1-SEN2	7635	19129	49786	125	42056
FZD5-GSK3A-SEN2	1856	36876	56727	30350	43628	FSHB-NKD1-SEN2	14879	5325	16207	3306	6877
DKK1-NKD1-SEN2	7012	22034	30235	20793	14207	FZD5-PYGO1-SEN2	864	25856	32614	26549	46981
SEN2-TLE1-TLE2	22393	22753	3266	25737	12237	FBXW11-NKD1-SEN2	3968	23882	33729	15929	5877
CSNK1D-FOXN1-SEN2	1289	8520	39455	7070	25852	FZD8-PORCN-SEN2	1042	32328	3606	28410	19273
FBXW11-GSK3B-SEN2	5753	10714	20625	19385	4353	DKK1-FSHB-SEN2	13659	23744	54431	4021	33075
DKK1-FRAT1-SEN2	5714	28221	7591	6962	28179	SEN2-WNT1-WNT2B	2021	43379	30860	2867	24069
FRZB-NKD1-SEN2	3644	10458	50187	29431	36573	CSNK1G1-DVL2-SEN2	10060	33044	6346	24081	29517
FBXW11-FGF4-SEN2	460	23321	17102	23270	7399	FRZB-LEF1-SEN2	306	25220	39312	10442	24101
NLK-PORCN-SEN2	25839	52725	11882	9881	37272	FZD5-FZD2-SEN2	5895	34287	41654	30068	50389
FZD1-FZD2-SEN2	4443	13047	26746	40642	49778	SEN2-SFRP1-WNT2B	12477	36645	18903	52949	54446
FOSL1-FOXN1-SEN2	1644	24800	52856	5786	32696	FBXW11-RHOA-SEN2	2811	29045	28581	338	17622
CSNK1G1-LRP5-SEN2	14135	47074	22615	10563	18356	CXXC4-JUN-SEN2	1851	32478	55139	8858	43014
CSNK1G1-JUN-SEN2	2057	43819	27038	14070	17638	FZD1-NKD1-SEN2	16283	248	42563	17609	26499
FRAT1-JUN-SEN2	8350	32873	42151	5535	36295	SEN2-WNT1-WNT4	595	42309	31627	659	12885
DVL1-FOXN1-SEN2	3061	30960	37499	23295	15142	FRAT1-PORCN-SEN2	1688	40659	28876	5431	52097
DVL1-FBXW11-SEN2	10393	17940	54581	8945	22213	APC-FZD2-SEN2	324	36486	16060	22102	42466
FZD5-CTNNB1P1-SEN2	4249	39970	22055	26513	16307	SEN2-FBXW4-WNT4	7957	13325	39354	38785	4122
AXIN1-FZD2-SEN2	8182	15407	16562	39363	47191	FRZB-FSHB-SEN2	5870	14328	41622	369	53440
FRZB-LRP6-SEN2	1809	20940	39489	3847	40248	DKK1-LEF1-SEN2	1211	36246	13554	12065	5713
CSNK1G1-FSHB-SEN2	41253	35360	30966	2443	33408	KREMEN1-PORCN-SEN2	2897	40815	14540	5841	26554
FZD7-GSK3A-SEN2	290	25036	52263	13397	4756	FSHB-GSK3A-SEN2	6015	32214	13032	15982	30339
FBXW11-JUN-SEN2	2521	15541	36470	25945	625	EP300-GSK3B-SEN2	8327	37174	36829	10925	19701
DIXDC1-LRP5-SEN2	1777	23484	44827	123	12925	DAAMI-GSK3A-SEN2	1185	54603	39296	24751	14243
FZD1-GSK3A-SEN2	1003	14896	54197	10418	35326	DIXDC1-FZD2-SEN2	11918	40028	27691	41589	5926
AXIN1-MYC-SEN2	26539	8188	46118	33138	43486	CTBP1-GSK3A-SEN2	409	42665	56908	22557	34169
FBXW2-PORCN-SEN2	9048	55175	828	25406	16023	FSHB-LEF1-SEN2	16486	20092	5835	4015	10968
GSK3B-RHOA-SEN2	5807	32711	51623	1013	46591	CSNK2A1-FOXN1-SEN2	142	13206	48212	17145	40808
FBXW2-JUN-SEN2	25289	51870	3972	20307	1098	CSNK1G1-NKD1-SEN2	4079	7354	54740	12528	13804
BTRC-GSK3A-SEN2	9345	20665	52714	11947	10821	FRZB-PYGO1-SEN2	334	16496	42795	31671	51686
FBXW11-FBXW2-SEN2	5640	29344	45548	27448	44741	FZD8-GSK3A-SEN2	422	12723	55867	1253	13272

Table 2: Rankings of SEN2-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - rbf

CSNK1G1-DVL2-SEN2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - 2002

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FBXW11-LRP6-SEN2	18816	1859	13586	9174	45307	DKK1-JUN-SEN2	754	9372	11904	1076	33385
CXXC4-PORCN-SEN2	4981	10546	9375	17394	34482	CSNK1D-FGF4-SEN2	45011	27585	30267	41354	22081
CSNK2A1-MYC-SEN2	5898	9120	7738	21203	48879	FOSL1-FRAT1-SEN2	11214	7586	5074	7384	41915
APC-FZD6-SEN2	33226	35992	50633	32654	8758	APC-PITX2-SEN2	16777	21369	5264	21757	43696
DVL2-JUN-SEN2	13471	27115	21910	19735	56433	FZD1-NLK-SEN2	32881	56429	40609	50897	13532
DKK1-DVL2-SEN2	51970	1807	50365	38224	12081	CSNK1G1-NLK-SEN2	14817	11675	2225	15674	28868
FZD7-NKD1-SEN2	1050	48745	26187	16335	39423	CCND2-LRP6-SEN2	48398	45642	48566	56547	4885
CXXC4-FOSL1-SEN2	9857	21302	3091	25681	49127	LRP5-NLK-SEN2	54975	52944	33505	52497	5925
FRZB-JUN-SEN2	12004	43333	28019	17227	24299	DKK1-LRP6-SEN2	466	9443	18645	24697	29039
DIXDC1-NKD1-SEN2	12200	40063	24628	25782	18022	CTBP2-CTNNB1-SEN2	10760	32191	20331	21094	33415
DAAMI-LRP6-SEN2	18313	6918	23128	13037	43622	FZD5-CCND2-SEN2	7109	29501	13442	6843	45069
FSHB-FZD2-SEN2	14802	30771	22388	3404	40748	FZD5-CCND3-SEN2	1450	18152	5712	22203	10871
FZD7-PORCN-SEN2	49164	36968	35726	42699	17480	DKK1-PYGO1-SEN2	5320	8965	25659	16677	34823
CSNK1D-PORCN-SEN2	26180	49740	24174	6964	30394	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SEN2	17310	2495	82	9104	48865
FRZB-MYC-SEN2	26570	24004	3337	4415	47299	AES-EP300-SEN2	27514	29223	14109	27550	56692
SEN2-FBXW4-WNT3A	32061	15253	50111	35264	22955	DKK1-MYC-SEN2	231	34135	15721	15716	50447
FBXW2-PYGO1-SEN2	19176	47463	19297	20507	39832	FRAT1-NLK-SEN2	30840	31831	43075	52500	657
FRZB-GSK3A-SEN2	31582	11041	39292	45096	1425	CXXC4-FGF4-SEN2	56902	51611	35174	38140	4316
DKK1-FOSL1-SEN2	3431	3346	23554	20246	9046	FZD5-PITX2-SEN2	521	47250	5679	3657	50275
DKK1-FOXN1-SEN2	15411	46643	24807	26053	15345	FOSL1-PORCN-SEN2	54760	25670	47342	32899	26575
FZD5-MYC-SEN2	25185	18203	1638	9725	50713	FOSL1-NLK-SEN2	13461	35727	546	20026	44857
DAAMI-PYGO1-SEN2	10224	2416	14099	12136	24858	FZD5-PORCN-SEN2	27413	45632	5424	7312	44530
FZD1-PORCN-SEN2	21577	45473	27023	26028	44572	FBXW11-FOXN1-SEN2	18268	562	25898	8742	43081
DKK1-PORCN-SEN2	7496	43787	13993	24495	52737	FRZB-FZD2-SEN2	37764	24560	31433	55891	44073
CSNK1G1-PORCN-SEN2	43281	37454	56745	49095	6460	CSNK1G1-FZD2-SEN2	11142	28642	7792	15597	42963
DKK1-PPP2R1A-SEN2	32867	41750	37757	38732	22794	CTNNBIP1-JUN-SEN2	15007	40205	17451	2535	40407
FOSL1-JUN-SEN2	51877	55400	52885	34018	3734	APC-PORCN-SEN2	19313	15156	9308	25386	44309
FRZB-PORCN-SEN2	13854	51961	26520	17468	45862	GSK3B-LRP6-SEN2	16382	8575	22031	15681	40828
DVL1-MYC-SEN2	7208	31944	15546	28136	11474	FZD5-FOXN1-SEN2	844	38547	5609	13856	38976
LRP5-PORCN-SEN2	14420	8910	7971	16494	35454	FZD6-PORCN-SEN2	2457	23664	19666	22956	54834
AES-FOXN1-SEN2	15326	21444	1720	26394	49021	DIXDC1-PITX2-SEN2	55978	6920	46363	55209	16814
FZD7-PPP2CA-SEN2	10937	22503	18140	21817	45345	BCL9-FGF4-SEN2	13001	45914	15316	22159	39102
FRZB-LRP5-SEN2	30626	31126	44247	54341	16858	CTBP2-FOXN1-SEN2	18763	34976	4397	1891	34643
FZD5-GSK3A-SEN2	50629	3550	54449	56850	11526	FSHB-NKD1-SEN2	15201	10828	10232	10064	44517
DKK1-NKD1-SEN2	52464	1370	44052	49768	19418	FZD5-PYGO1-SEN2	10582	54199	15471	9662	50406
SEN2-TLE1-TLE2	23913	35038	906	601	42226	FBXW11-NKD1-SEN2	43774	38481	39045	45242	3193
CSNK1D-FOXN1-SEN2	22145	41275	26967	5135	47598	FZD8-PORCN-SEN2	124	56299	17625	6462	53950
FBXW11-GSK3B-SEN2	29051	55683	38484	45293	9816	DKK1-FSHB-SEN2	25567	47671	11467	15785	31909
DKK1-FRAT1-SEN2	45931	9787	52534	55862	16571	SEN2-WNT1-WNT2B	31781	23905	56648	48582	12552
FRZB-NKD1-SEN2	45346	338	32222	51005	1360	CSNK1G1-DVL2-SEN2	22798	50683	12430	15447	46966
FBXW11-FGF4-SEN2	28909	51819	40008	56796	37793	FRZB-LEF1-SEN2	30085	37802	47912	52349	35108
NLK-PORCN-SEN2	700	5829	4828	22993	34644	FZD5-FZD2-SEN2	48588	1244	55020	56471	32202
FZD1-FZD2-SEN2	40680	55685	34299	49655	21030	SEN2-SFRP1-WNT2B	7482	33180	11485	14807	20446
FOSL1-FOXN1-SEN2	50427	48059	30743	46224	6709	FBXW11-RHO-SEN2	24228	6117	12293	6320	49693
CSNK1G1-LRP5-SEN2	20952	26227	18132	5105	9267	CXXC4-JUN-SEN2	8825	8401	12932	7871	27023
CSNK1G1-JUN-SEN2	49955	51075	54767	43231	2180	FZD1-NKD1-SEN2	43989	55534	37195	51478	14369
FRAT1-JUN-SEN2	10491	7985	11945	814	56174	SEN2-WNT1-WNT4	27482	37862	8657	159	32055
DVL1-FOXN1-SEN2	16471	55562	16915	23813	45857	FRAT1-PORCN-SEN2	8802	23948	15600	4011	48205
DVL1-FBXW11-SEN2	27901	46069	5017	11244	34009	APC-FZD2-SEN2	38485	51551	36146	40579	5446
FZD5-CTNNBIP1-SEN2	6073	19524	14174	19205	11084	SEN2-FBXW4-WNT4	14841	33195	5632	25971	23429
AXIN1-FZD2-SEN2	50604	19396	54661	51956	4154	FRZB-FSHB-SEN2	16157	4030	19992	6634	56588
FRZB-LRP6-SEN2	26487	29946	10450	5459	45249	DKK1-LEF1-SEN2	50244	16308	44258	33178	21539
CSNK1G1-FSHB-SEN2	47318	7617	44202	35329	27387	KREMEN1-PORCN-SEN2	1460	11304	1074	20122	52679
FZD7-GSK3A-SEN2	20	7133	26728	22595	30127	FSHB-GSK3A-SEN2	25073	23609	16769	2541	50098
FBXW11-JUN-SEN2	27619	7495	18431	13804	56624	EP300-GSK3B-SEN2	26252	6795	3095	116	51289
DIXDC1-LRP5-SEN2	4268	28488	25270	8378	13292	DAAMI-GSK3A-SEN2	38843	54272	41288	35952	24222
FZD1-GSK3A-SEN2	30966	45020	36158	50118	5672	DIXDC1-FZD2-SEN2	6691	25178	18767	17941	39342
AXIN1-MYC-SEN2	6950	1767	3485	7734	36502	CTBP1-GSK3A-SEN2	30054	20556	48227	41103	28895
FBXW2-PORCN-SEN2	25417	49706	4981	6457	55941	FSHB-LEF1-SEN2	20816	17194	23144	10318	20084
GSK3B-RHO-SEN2	374	11610	27039	12714	39384	CSNK2A1-FOXN1-SEN2	9019	3852	10133	23930	23783
FBXW2-JUN-SEN2	10475	4057	14601	2973	45279	CSNK1G1-NKD1-SEN2	8054	22379	116	14940	56704
BTRC-GSK3A-SEN2	49345	53825	50292	50442	26863	FRZB-PYGO1-SEN2	11932	6986	25367	12616	52422
FBXW11-FBXW2-SEN2	41323	52817	46697	38722	2918	FZD8-GSK3A-SEN2	46851	22033	37672	51251	4003

Table 3: Rankings of SEN2-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - 2002

6.3.3. Examining the behaviour of GSK3-SEN2-X combinations

Next, since the formation of complex of DVL with AXIN does not happen, as SEN2 combines with AXIN, GSK3 phosphorylates β -catenin and there is inhibition of the

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - MARTINEZ

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
FBXW11-LRP6-SEN2	48732	31543	56554	35694	23187	DKK1-JUN-SEN2	39293	26785	2472	17869	34742
CXXC4-PORCN-SEN2	17800	21889	46576	9816	38838	CSNK1D-FGF4-SEN2	55119	28784	753	23302	53897
CSNK2A1-MYC-SEN2	25707	12898	3554	47825	33675	FOSL1-FRAT1-SEN2	39777	6057	7944	11007	26753
APC-FZD6-SEN2	26727	48049	30387	43086	13904	APC-PITX2-SEN2	8228	7160	4560	17437	34258
DVL2-JUN-SEN2	35230	56370	12983	26309	6576	FZD1-NLK-SEN2	38601	38210	1256	1993	12948
DKK1-DVL2-SEN2	14103	26632	42161	55002	30870	CSNK1G1-NLK-SEN2	1023	28963	23752	12006	13662
FZD7-NKD1-SEN2	35427	30303	49552	55744	274	CCND2-LRP6-SEN2	35837	18793	41733	44193	44439
CXXC4-FOSL1-SEN2	7660	26757	51210	21967	12513	LRP5-NLK-SEN2	20156	45164	15815	450	10120
FRZB-JUN-SEN2	4353	41972	31373	42600	6952	DKK1-LRP6-SEN2	40550	20641	39972	43257	48887
DIXDC1-NKD1-SEN2	6022	11818	20358	22850	47306	CTBP2-CTNNB1-SEN2	52153	13962	45501	2019	49580
DAAMI-LRP6-SEN2	28461	26026	28743	36544	45562	FZD5-CCND2-SEN2	29534	13121	34325	22159	329
FSHB-FZD2-SEN2	4678	20262	6383	27755	44142	FZD5-CCND3-SEN2	33481	50646	50001	33032	2858
FZD7-PORCN-SEN2	17938	34334	1378	26310	39548	DKK1-PYGO1-SEN2	44254	18975	35893	25046	32000
CSNK1D-PORCN-SEN2	1456	4258	8869	32822	29157	FOSL1-PPP2R1A-SEN2	53756	53724	17611	16937	2010
FRZB-MYC-SEN2	11312	48614	33526	26319	1360	AES-EP300-SEN2	3503	32175	28924	49375	20292
SEN2-FBXW4-WNT3A	16928	95	53827	44450	47650	DKK1-MYC-SEN2	10451	52848	3280	17554	47121
FBXW2-PYGO1-SEN2	3761	16157	15508	5360	43710	FRAT1-NLK-SEN2	23247	35162	2221	25952	18481
FRZB-GSK3A-SEN2	23469	49325	11207	20330	9793	CXXC4-FGF4-SEN2	56684	55582	53323	1516	51115
DKK1-FOSL1-SEN2	39859	13212	23188	18065	7821	FZD5-PITX2-SEN2	41803	45522	15594	45235	8865
DKK1-FOXN1-SEN2	168	13005	4602	14511	33848	FOSL1-PORCN-SEN2	12075	2582	50306	27092	37213
FZD5-MYC-SEN2	34766	55243	6601	22504	28242	FOSL1-NLK-SEN2	39240	18008	8851	50840	47605
DAAMI-PYGO1-SEN2	36499	23008	51614	13246	37650	FZD5-PORCN-SEN2	4057	36674	11079	4102	30265
FZD1-PORCN-SEN2	16152	22375	9599	2134	53565	FBXW11-FOXN1-SEN2	15519	50540	42098	37233	6768
DKK1-PORCN-SEN2	45052	7054	16503	35722	44298	FRZB-FZD2-SEN2	35657	54239	11501	555	13723
CSNK1G1-PORCN-SEN2	15610	15039	24692	32268	17031	CSNK1G1-FZD2-SEN2	23323	8023	15244	20763	9314
DKK1-PPP2R1A-SEN2	5672	4114	48876	17608	30388	CTNNB1P1-JUN-SEN2	24218	24078	19550	5942	13375
FOSL1-JUN-SEN2	11684	1590	49191	41693	56255	APC-PORCN-SEN2	22313	13751	17377	17470	16927
FRZB-PORCN-SEN2	5700	39274	27314	56378	56042	GSK3B-LRP6-SEN2	2454	38736	45076	55913	4393
DVL1-MYC-SEN2	7295	2101	7917	7041	49481	FZD5-FOXN1-SEN2	40428	20162	38623	7744	42912
LRP5-PORCN-SEN2	27087	24353	54744	56478	25297	FZD6-PORCN-SEN2	32912	3888	24013	2296	408
AES-FOXN1-SEN2	39680	6172	11814	7048	33251	DIXDC1-PITX2-SEN2	22480	35744	10230	30579	35447
FZD7-PPP2CA-SEN2	20018	21717	46184	2450	53554	BCL9-FGF4-SEN2	46101	14098	4221	3152	6654
FRZB-LRP5-SEN2	22995	41293	21854	3067	9017	CTBP2-FOXN1-SEN2	32469	35593	13053	16587	40403
FZD5-GSK3A-SEN2	20016	37026	42778	13795	50467	FSHB-NKD1-SEN2	26326	50101	3632	18950	54806
DKK1-NKD1-SEN2	11947	15501	1575	31335	38725	FZD5-PYGO1-SEN2	22699	16430	36618	55374	27834
SEN2-TLE1-TLE2	19141	40024	43492	12120	24127	FBXW11-NKD1-SEN2	55745	36584	9866	51299	52063
CSNK1D-FOXN1-SEN2	38843	9650	25689	48746	11032	FZD8-PORCN-SEN2	51735	28846	18836	25156	31908
FBXW11-GSK3B-SEN2	39302	369	1110	1651	33514	DKK1-FSHB-SEN2	1237	22131	34620	28281	43154
DKK1-FRAT1-SEN2	14696	24294	9121	27635	46653	SEN2-WNT1-WNT2B	16555	17079	41227	9388	56362
FRZB-NKD1-SEN2	55847	31620	30451	51922	16894	CSNK1G1-DVL2-SEN2	2829	8071	56530	44158	5270
FBXW11-FGF4-SEN2	14371	1465	51095	30476	39794	FRZB-LEF1-SEN2	15749	34474	6078	7026	7697
NLK-PORCN-SEN2	9588	21743	36008	30568	4545	FZD5-FZD2-SEN2	24477	12748	50071	377	41286
FZD1-FZD2-SEN2	10037	43715	10301	844	13590	SEN2-SFRP1-WNT2B	40240	50851	56622	9242	9004
FOSL1-FOXN1-SEN2	16250	40283	38179	32075	20042	FBXW11-RHOA-SEN2	10035	17928	5691	56523	4295
CSNK1G1-LRP5-SEN2	430	22598	40400	16862	29795	CXXC4-JUN-SEN2	45684	29715	54947	14159	18626
CSNK1G1-JUN-SEN2	53562	32056	34894	40476	27708	FZD1-NKD1-SEN2	49139	38431	23193	31391	8701
FRAT1-JUN-SEN2	25462	55027	16547	2227	53156	SEN2-WNT1-WNT4	23302	15994	3637	19774	7442
DVL1-FOXN1-SEN2	6587	3940	24129	7079	19484	FRAT1-PORCN-SEN2	18609	31024	10863	13050	55318
DVL1-FBXW11-SEN2	17753	26234	19655	16825	19022	APC-FZD2-SEN2	42287	45890	35128	44793	29082
FZD5-CTNNB1P1-SEN2	35572	26403	19918	19567	8759	SEN2-FBXW4-WNT4	30943	9589	56816	22982	2735
AXIN1-FZD2-SEN2	37222	18163	43383	10854	29251	FRZB-FSHB-SEN2	39025	16786	12898	8014	29180
FRZB-LRP6-SEN2	7569	55561	4984	17049	45518	DKK1-LEF1-SEN2	10401	5154	50212	43911	40635
FRZB-FSHB-SEN2	32972	50887	28581	8306	20113	KREMEN1-PORCN-SEN2	53256	34131	37244	42862	23394
FZD7-GSK3A-SEN2	14840	14837	40840	51841	1213	FSHB-GSK3A-SEN2	7731	54453	20490	20338	36146
FBXW11-JUN-SEN2	9156	15077	6177	1681	2691	EP300-GSK3B-SEN2	20604	44330	12414	20857	50439
DIXDC1-LRP5-SEN2	11654	7229	13083	25007	48199	DAAMI-GSK3A-SEN2	36657	23964	7865	43674	16691
FZD1-GSK3A-SEN2	28569	43692	49593	18370	22695	DIXDC1-FZD2-SEN2	27322	44564	29539	36845	42568
AXIN1-MYC-SEN2	28562	52012	47388	14183	46587	CTBP1-GSK3A-SEN2	19634	32533	39315	3902	38573
FBXW2-PORCN-SEN2	47052	53728	12174	17062	31361	FSHB-LEF1-SEN2	110	43538	5716	50939	40396
GSK3B-RHOA-SEN2	45704	3857	31271	32707	133	CSNK2A1-FOXN1-SEN2	14555	16853	56191	37447	12743
FBXW2-JUN-SEN2	44868	6548	55912	21346	1004	CSNK1G1-NKD1-SEN2	5658	19388	11502	16684	22979
BTRC-GSK3A-SEN2	39429	55220	2991	34867	49837	FRZB-PYGO1-SEN2	29413	11451	18530	12785	54338
FBXW11-FBXW2-SEN2	57032	5605	7832	17912	32452	FZD8-GSK3A-SEN2	24206	17342	32476	29923	7916

Table 4: Rankings of SENP2-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - martinez

WNT signaling pathway. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of the GSK3 family along with SENP2, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FRZB-GSK3A-SEN2, FZD5-GSK3A-SEN2, FBXW11-GSK3B-SEN2,

FZD7-GSK3A-SEN2, FZD1-GSK3A-SEN2, GSK3B-RHO-SEN2, BTRC-GSK3A-SEN2, GSK3B-LRP6-SEN2, FSHB-GSK3A-SEN2, EP300-GSK3B-SEN2, DAAM1-GSK3A-SEN2, CTBP1-GSK3A-SEN2 and FZD8-GSK3A-SEN2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.4. Examining the behaviour of JUN-SEN2-X combinations

c-JUN plays an important role in regulating cell growth, apoptosis, differentiation, and transformation. Its transcriptional activity can be regulated by both phosphorylation and sumoylation. It has also been shown that c-JUN transcription can be regulated by SuPr-1, an alternatively spliced form of SEN2. Cheng et al. [15] show that SEN1 enhances the transcription activity of c-JUN. They found that the action of SEN1 on c-JUN transcription is independent of the sumoylation and phosphorylation status of c-JUN but is critically dependent on the desumoylation activity of SEN1. Further, they show that p300 is essential for SEN1 to enhance c-JUN-dependent transcription because SEN1 can desumoylate the CRD1 domain of p300, thereby releasing the cis-repression of CRD1 on p300.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for JUN along with SEN2, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DVL2-JUN-SEN2, FRZB-JUN-SEN2, FOSL1-JUN-SEN2, CSNK1G1-JUN-SEN2, FRAT1-JUN-SEN2, FBXW11-JUN-SEN2, FBXW2-JUN-SEN2, DKK1-JUN-SEN2, CTNNBIP1-JUN-SEN2 and CXXC4-JUN-SEN2. Also, looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for EP300 (or p300) along with SEN2, to be prominent at 3rd order level - AES-EP300-SEN2 and EP300-GSK3B-SEN2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.5. Examining the behaviour of FOX-SEN2-X combinations

Transcription factor forkhead box protein P2 (FOXP2) plays an essential role in the development of language and speech. Meredith et al. [16] demonstrated that FOXP2 undergoes post-translational modification as it is a SUMO target protein at the cellular levels as FOXP2 is covalently modified by both SUMO1 and SUMO3. Furthermore, they observe that SUMOylation of FOXP2 was significantly decreased by SEN2. Wang et al. [17] observed that when SEN2 was co-expressed with FOXM1B and SUMO1 in cells, the SUMOylated band was completely lost, which suggested that SEN2 was involved in mediating the de-SUMOylation of FOXM1B. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of FOX family along with SEN2, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DKK1-FOXN1-SEN2, AES-FOXN1-SEN2, CSNK1D-FOXN1-SEN2, FOSL1-FOXN1-SEN2, DVL1-FOXN1-SEN2, FBXW11-FOXN1-SEN2, FZD5-FOXN1-SEN2, CTBP2-FOXN1-SEN2 and CSNK2A1-FOXN1-SEN2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.6. Examining the behaviour of CCND-SENP2-X combinations

Several proteins have been suggested to have diverse impact on insulin synthesis and secretion through SUMO modification in β cells. Jung et al. [18] examined the changes in expression of SENP in INS1 cells and pancreatic islets under diabetes-relevant stress conditions and associated changes in β cell mass. Treatment with 25 mM glucose for 72 h induced SENP2 mRNA expression but not that of SENP1 in INS1 cells. Immunohistochemical staining with anti-SENP2 antibody on human pancreas sections revealed that SENP2 was localized in the nucleus and in a patient with type 2 diabetes, SENP2 levels were enhanced, especially in the cytoplasm. They observed that cell number peaked earlier in INS1 cells cultured in high-glucose conditions compared to those cultured in control media. These findings were associated with increased CCND1 mRNA expression in high-glucose conditions, and siRNA-mediated SENP2 suppression abrogated it. In conclusion, they observed that SENP2 may play a role in β cell mass in response to chronic high-glucose through CCND1 and MAFA.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of FOX family along with SENP2, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CCND2-LRP6-SENP2, FZD5-CCND2-SENP2 and FZD5-CCND3-SENP2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.7. Examining the behaviour of CTNNB-SENP2-X combinations

Tang et al. [19] found that SENP2 was decreased in hepatocellular carcinoma HCC cell lines (including Hep3B, Li7, and Huh7) compared with normal human liver epithelial cell lines, which was further reduced in HCC stem cells than in normal HCC cells. They observed that SENP2 overexpression inhibited CD133⁺ cell proportion, decreased sphere formation ability, promoted sorafenib sensitivity, suppressed AKT and GSK3 β phosphorylation, and reduced CTNNB1 expression in Huh7 and Hep3B cells, while SENP2 knockdown showed the reverse effects.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for CTNNB1 along with SENP2, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CTBP2-CTNNB1-SENP2. Moreover, CTNNBIP1 (inhibitor of β -catenin and TCF4), binds CTNNB1 and prevents interaction between CTNNB1 and TCF (T-cell transcription factor) family members. The encoded protein is a negative regulator of the Wnt signaling pathway. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for CTNNBIP1 along with SENP2, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CTNNBIP1-JUN-SENP2 and FZD5-CTNNBIP1-SENP2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

7. Conclusion

This manuscript studies the time behaviour of 3rd order combinations of SENP2 in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells. Based on the established 2nd order combinations of the SENP2, 3rd order combinations emerge using the machine learning based search

engine. These 3rd order combinations might be of interest for further wet lab investigations.

Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

Author contributions statement

SS conceived and designed the experiments; wrote the code; performed the experiments; analyzed the data; wrote the manuscript.

Availability of code

Code for time series data available at CERN based Zenodo on <https://zenodo.org/records/14637456>.

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Supplementary

The following files (ending with .txt and can be opened in R or in simple text processing program) with these names are made available with this manuscript. For SENP2, (1) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-linear.txt**, (2) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-rbf.txt**, (3) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-2002.txt**, and (4) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-martinez.txt**, contain rankings for 3rd order combinations across each time point for, HSIC (linear kernel), HSIC (rbf kernel), SOBOL (2002 implementation) and SOBOL (martinez implementation), respectively.

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